

1,3-Dioxolo[4,5-g]thiadiazolo[2,3-b]quinazolin-7-one

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Manuscript received 19 September 1986, revised 23 July 1987, accepted 30 October 1987

6-Nitropiperonyl chloride (1), on reaction with *N*-carbethoxyhydrazine (2) followed by reduction with tin and concentrated HCl gave ethyl 2-[(6-amino-1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)methyl]hydrazinecarboxylate (4) which on treatment with HCl and KSCN and subsequent cyclisation resulted in the formation of 7,8-dihydro-10*H*-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]thiadiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-7-one (5).

LITERATURE records¹⁻⁸ the synthesis of some thiadiazoloquinazolines and some of the compounds in this series have shown good amoebicidal and anti-inflammatory activity. It was thought of interest to introduce a dioxole ring in this system and herein we report the synthesis of yet another unknown system, namely 1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]thiadiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-7-one.

The condensation of 6-nitropiperonyl chloride (1) with *N*-carbethoxyhydrazine (2), led to the formation of ethyl 2-[(6-nitro-1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)methyl]hydrazinecarboxylate (3) which on reduction with tin and concentrated HCl was converted into ethyl 2-[(6-amino-1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)methyl]hydrazinecarboxylate (4). On passing dry HCl through a solution of 4 followed by reaction with KSCN in boiling ethanol, it gave 7,8-dihydro-10*H*-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]thiadiazolo[2,3-*b*]quinazolin-7-one (5). The structures of 3-5 was characterised by ir, pmr and elemental analyses.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in liquid paraffin-bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621, and pmr spectra on a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using TMS as the internal reference.

Ethyl 2-[(6-nitro-1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)methyl]hydrazinecarboxylate (3): 6-Nitropiperonyl chloride⁹ (10.77 g, 0.05 mol) and *N*-carbethoxyhydrazine (10.4 g, 0.1 mol) were mixed thoroughly at room temperature and the temperature was then raised to 50-60°. After 20 min of heating, the mobile liquid changed to a thick sticky mass. Heating was

continued for 3 h for the completion of the reaction. After cooling, the mass was washed with water to remove excess of *N*-carbethoxyhydrazine. The product was collected by filtration under suction, dried and crystallised from absolute ethanol into yellow coloured needles yield (8.80 g, 81.7%), m.p. 122° (Found: C, 43.00; H, 4.30; N, 14.45. C₁₁H₁₃N₃O₆ requires: C, 43.10; H, 4.23; N, 14.44%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 655 (C=O of the ester) and 3 400-3 450 (N-H's); δ (CDCl₃) 7.55(1H, s, C₇-H Ar), 7.18(1H, s, C₄-H Ar), 6.40(1H, bs, NH-COO), 6.21(2H, s, OCH₂O), 4.00-4.41(4H, m, Ar-CH₂+COOCH₂CH₃), 2.92(1H, bs, NHCH₂) and 1.30(3H, t, OCH₂CH₃) (NH exchangeable with D₂O).

Ethyl 2-[(6-amino-1,3-benzodioxol-5-yl)methyl]hydrazinecarboxylate (4): To a mixture of finely granulated tin metal (1 g) and 3 (1 g) was added concentrated HCl (10 ml) in small portions with continuous stirring. The reaction was highly exothermic and temperature rose to 40-45°. After keeping it as such for 20 min, it was heated on a steam-bath for 45 min, when all the tin dissolved. It was cooled in an ice-bath and basified with saturated solution of sodium hydroxide. The reduced product was isolated by extracting it with ether (10×40 ml). The ether extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. On evaporation of ether, a dark brown sticky mass was obtained which upon crystallisation from a mixture of petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and ether gave grey needles yield (0.270 g, 30%), m.p. 170° (Found: C, 52.15; H, 5.90; N, 16.59. C₁₁H₁₃N₃O₄ requires: C, 52.10; H, 5.92; N, 16.60%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1 650 (C=O of the ester) and 3 400-3 480 (NH's); δ (CDCl₃) 7.41(1H, s, C₄-H Ar), 6.90(1H, s, C₇-H Ar), 6.39(1H, bs, NH-C), 6.23(2H, s, OCH₂O), 3.80-4.18(7H, m, ArCH₂+OCH₂CH₃+ArNH₂+NHCH₂) and 1.30(3H, t, OCH₂CH₃).

7,8-Dihydro-10*H*-1,3-dioxolo[4,5-*g*]thiadiazolo[4,3-*b*]quinazolin-7-one (5): A slow stream of dry HCl was passed through the chilled ethereal suspension of 4 (253 mg) till it was saturated. Ether was decanted off and the residue was suspended in

absolute ethanol (20 ml). To it an aqueous solution (1 ml) of KSCN (116 mg, 0.0012 mol) was added and the contents were refluxed on a steam-bath for 3 h. On cooling, a dark brown mass separated out. It was collected under suction, and crystallisation from ethanol gave dark brown needles (0.190 g, 75%), m.p. 191° (Found: C, 48.17; H, 2.84; N, 16.81. $C_{10}H_7N_3O_3S$ requires: C, 48.19; H, 2.81; N, 16.88%); ν_{max} (nujol) 1660 (CONH) and 3380 (NH); δ ($CDCl_3 + TFA$), 6.53 (2H, d, C_4-H and C_7-H Ar), 6.05 (2H, s, OCH_2O) and 4.65 (2H, s, $ArCH_2$).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. S. V. Kessar, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, for facilities. One of the authors (J.K.G.)

is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

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